

Paper: GLOGIFT 22
**Best in some ways but not others: Paradox of stagnant institutional
competitiveness despite competitive individuals**

Pranav Mukund Bhat
Department of Metallurgical Engineering and Materials Science,
Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai,
Maharashtra, Pin: 400 076
Email ID: 210110034@iitb.ac.in

Rishabh Raj Jain
Department of Metallurgical Engineering and Materials Science,
Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai,
Maharashtra, Pin: 400 076
Email ID: 210110091@iitb.ac.in

Padmanav Adhikari
Shailesh J. Mehta School of Management,
Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai,
Maharashtra, Pin: 400 076
Email ID: padmanav.adhikari@iitb.ac.in
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4594-019X>

Abstract

Indian Institute of Technology Bombay (IITB in short) is one of the oldest premier technical public educational institutions in India that is regularly featured in many national and international rankings. However, despite being home to some of the brightest minds in the country and despite possessing very mature processes the institute seems to have stagnated massively on multiple fronts. In this exploratory study, we present the indicative findings of a preliminary research conducted to collect and compile evidence to better understand the said paradox.

Keywords

Institutional competitiveness, paradox, organizational flexibility, start-up competitiveness

Sub-theme

Firm Competitiveness

Paper: GLOGIFT 22
Best in some ways but not others: Paradox of stagnant institutional competitiveness despite competitive individuals

1. Introduction

Indian Institute of Technology Bombay (IITB in short) is one of the oldest premier technical public educational institutions in India. Recognized worldwide as a leader in education and research in engineering, sciences, management, design, and other fields, IITB attracts the best students from the country and abroad. Declared to be an institution of national importance by the government of India, it is regularly featured in many national and international rankings (Prasad et al., 2019)—including NIRF¹ India Rankings, QS World University Rankings², and ARWU Rankings³.

However, despite being home to some of the brightest minds in the country and despite possessing mature processes, the institute seems to be underperforming massively on several fronts—be it entrepreneurship or research, and teaching or outreach (Momaya et al., 2017). Extant studies have identified both systemic (e.g., institute-levels gaps in strategic flexibility, Momaya et al., 2017) and individualistic (e.g., academic demotivation, Prasad et al., 2019; inadequate focus on health and fitness, Tale et al., 2020) reasons for the same. However, most studies have glossed over the paradoxical stagnation of institutional competitiveness despite the presence of world-class assets (i.e., bright students) and mature processes. This is the research gap we seek to address in this exploratory study. Herein, we present the indicative findings of a preliminary research conducted to collect and compile evidence to better understand the aforementioned paradox. We limit the scope of our analysis to the specific context of entrepreneurial and business leadership stagnation wherein we try to factually understand the seemingly diminishing contribution of students and alumni of IITB towards founding and scaling up sustainable enterprises. In doing so, we take a practice-oriented (and not a research-focused) approach to better delineate the phenomenon of premature stagnation of institutions wherein some organizations seem to underperform despite the presence of superior resources and matured processes.

2. Literature Review

Keeping in mind the practice-oriented nature of this study, “a purposive literature review with a defined scope was undertaken” (p. 1402, Tale et al., 2020). Here, we lay out the findings of a select few of them.

Competitiveness is a ‘multi-layered’ concept that can be studied at many levels (Adhikari &

¹ The National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF in short) is a framework adopted by the Ministry of Education (Government of India) to rank institutes of higher education in India.

² QS World University Rankings is a ranking of universities, all across the globe that is published by Quacquarelli Symonds, a British company that specializes in the analysis of higher education institutions.

³ The Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU in short), also known as ‘Shanghai Ranking’ or ‘ARWU-Shanghai Ranking’ is an annual publication of world university rankings published by ShanghaiRanking Consultancy.

Momaya, 2021)—be it at the country, the industry, or the firm/institutional level. Owing to its ‘multi-defined’ and ‘multi-measured’ nature, the construct of competitiveness is very hard to operationalize (Chaudhuri & Ray, 1997). However, the novel competitiveness assets-processes-performance (C-APP) framework (Momaya, 2001) provides a relatively simple but comprehensive structure that can be used to understand the drivers of competitiveness performance across levels. According to this framework, any organization is a combination of input (assets), throughput (process), and output (performance) sub-systems and improving the input and/or the throughput sub-systems help organizations improve their performance. However, the paradoxical inability of IITB to catch up to its international peers despite possessing world-class assets and mature processes (Momaya, 2014) marks an interesting departure from this prescription and presents an interesting opportunity for theory extension.

To understand the aforementioned dilemma better, we first referred to a study that looked into institute-level factors such as low strategic flexibility (Momaya et al., 2017). While helpful, the study only considered two internal actors, ‘top management’ and ‘faculty’. To understand the possible reasons from the point-of-view of students (another important stakeholder for any educational institution), we referred to a study that tried to understand the reasons behind the academic demotivation of students of premier educational institutions (Prasad et al., 2019). We could get a lot of insights on the student-level (i.e., individual) causes that might lead to poor institution-level competitiveness performance from this study. However, the studies we referred to did not consider leadership success and sustainability as a proxy of institutional competitiveness.

To summarize, we discovered that not many studies have tried to address institutional stagnation of educational institutions such as IITB by taking into account the success and sustainability of startups founded or led by students and alumni of such institutions.

3. Research Methodology

Our study is qualitative in nature. It used archival data from multiple sources to triangulate the inferences drawn from our secondary data analysis (Momaya et al., 2017). We undertook a quick benchmarking (QBM) exercise wherein we compared IITB with a select few institutions of national importance in India and a few other carefully selected premier educational institutions from across the world. We employed the QS World Rankings and NIRF India overall rankings for this exercise. Though not as exhaustive as a detailed benchmarking exercise (e.g., Bhattacharya et al., 2020) it helped us get a glimpse of the issues facing IITB. We also benchmarked the entrepreneurial and business leadership success of IITB against the previously selected institutions of national importance. This was done by analyzing the contribution of IITB (in terms of the number of founders or leaders who were alumni of IITB) for a carefully sampled group of top 100 firms⁴ that were founded in the last 25 years. Data required for this exercise was collected from

⁴ Top 100 firms by revenue

CMIE ProwessIQ and Refinitiv Eikon. We also relied on a few popular websites⁵ to collect a preliminary sample of inspirational leaders.

4. Indicative Findings

In this section, we lay out the early-stage indicative findings of our initial QBM exercise.

Figure 1: QS Scores of IITB and its peers along the six facets

(a) Descriptive findings: Rankings

IITB fares considerably lower than its international peers in terms of its ‘International Student Ratio’ and ‘International Faculty Ratio’. While ‘Employer Reputation’ is good, work needs to be done on the ‘Academic Reputation’, as there is a gap visible in the kind of alumni that IITB has and the corresponding reputation it holds.

Figure 2: NIRF scores for select few institutions of national importance

⁵ Examples include: Global Leadership Today (GLT; [link](#))

IITB had maintained its top rank in NIRF for several years, but recently IIT Madras and IISc Bangalore have surpassed it after rigorously improving their research outputs. The peer perception has also increased for these two. While IIT Bombay is still ranked third, IIT Delhi is progressing fast and might overtake IITB in the coming years if IITB does not improve on its outputs in the given criteria.

(b) Descriptive findings: Entrepreneurial/leadership success

An exploratory analysis of some inspirational global leaders (as per GLT) revealed that very few leaders of Indian origin made it to the list. Even among a filtered sample of 10 such Indian leaders, only two belonged to IITB (see *Table 1*). This seems inadequate, especially for an institution of national importance. Similar trends are visible even in new-age firms and startups as can be inferred from *Table 2*.

Table 1: Inspirational Leaders of Indian Origin and their alma mater (as per GLT)

Name	Company	College/University
Mukesh Ambani	Reliance	University of Mumbai
Satya Nadella	Microsoft	MIT, Manipal
Sundar Pichai	Google	IIT Kharagpur
Reshma Saujani	Girls Who Code	Harvard University
Leena Nair	Chanel	Xavier (XLRI), Jharkand
Parag Aggarwal	Twitter	IIT Bombay
Lakshmi Mittal	Aperam	University of Calcutta
Deepinder Goyal	Zomato	IIT Delhi
Vandana Luthra	VLCC	Delhi University
Nandan Nilekani	Infosys, Aadhar	IIT Bombay

Table 2: Alma mater of a select few founders and leaders of new-age firms and startups

Company	Name	Education
CRED	Kunal Shah	Wilson College
Vernacular.ai	Sourabh Gupta, Akshay Deshraj, Prateek Gupta and Manoj Sarda	IIT Roorkee
PharmEasy	Siddharth Shah	IIM Ahmedabad
Digit Insurance	Kamesh Goyal	St Stephen's College
Meesho	Vidit Atreya, Sanjeev Barnwal	IIT Delhi
Groww	Lalit Keshre	IIT Bombay
Nykaa	Falguni Nayar	IIM-A, Sydenham College
Udaan	Vaibhav Gupta	IIT Delhi
Dream11	Harsh Jain	Pennsylvania University
Swiggy	Sriharsha Majety, Nandan Reddy, Rahul Jaimini	Bits Pilani

5. Concluding Remarks

Facts collected in our exploratory study shed some light on the institutional stagnation of IITB. Addressing the paradoxical gap of stagnant institutional competitiveness despite the presence of world-class assets and processes would not only help us solve a practical problem facing institutions of national importance but also take us a little closer to resolving a theoretical tension. Identifying the root cause behind premature institutional competitiveness performance would help institutions such as IITB in catching up with their internationally competitive peers (Momaya, 2014; Sharma & Jain, 2014) and would be a meaningful first step toward thinking differently (Momaya, 2020) about sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures originating from or being led by the students and/or alumni of such institutions. Moreover, uncovering why some organizations with superior assets and the best-in-class processes continue to underperform vis-à-vis their peers can augment the utility of the already exhaustively-tested C-APP framework.

6. References

- Adhikari, P., & Momaya, K. S. (2021). Innovation Capabilities, Environmentally Sustainable Practices and Export Competitiveness: An Exploratory Study of Firms From India. *International Journal of Innovation and Technology Management*, 18(06), 2150035. <https://doi.org/10.1142/s0219877021500358>
- Chaudhuri, S. and Ray, S. (1997). The competitiveness conundrum: Literature review and reflections. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 32(48): M83–M91.
- Bhattacharya, S., Momaya, K.S. & Iyer, K.C. (2020). Benchmarking enablers to achieve growth performance: a conceptual framework. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 27(4), 1475-1501. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-08-2019-0376>
- Momaya, K. S. (2001). *International competitiveness: Evaluation and enhancement*. New Delhi: Hindustan Publishing Corporation.
- Momaya, K. S. (2014). A New Perspective for Industrial Competitiveness: Exploring the Role of IITs. In M. K. Nandakumar, S. Jharkharia, & A. S. Nair (Eds.), *Organisational Flexibility and Competitiveness* (pp. 91–100). Springer India. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-81-322-1668-1_7
- Momaya, K. S., Bhat, S., & Lalwani, L. (2017). Institutional Growth and Industrial Competitiveness: Exploring the Role of Strategic Flexibility Taking the Case of Select Institutes in India. *Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management*, 18(2), 111–122. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40171-016-0144-2>
- Momaya, K.S. (2020). Return from COVID-19: Thinking Differently About Export Competitiveness and Sustainability. *International Journal of Global Business and Competitiveness* 15, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42943-020-00012-6>
- Prasad, M., Sengupta, S., & Niranjana, T. T. (2019). A peek into academic (de)motivation of undergraduates at India's top engineering schools. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 45(4), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2019.1586837>
- Sharma, R., & Jain, A. (2014). Research and patenting in Indian universities and technical institutes: An exploratory study. *World Patent Information*, 38, 62–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wpi.2014.04.002>
- Tale, N., Johari, C., Thapliyal, R., Adhikari, P., & Momaya, K. S. (2020). Grassroot innovations for institute flexibility: Leveraging management of technology to improve learner health through regular practices. In L. Pretorius & M. W. Pretorius (Eds.), *Towards the Digital World and Industry X.0, IAMOT 2020* (Vol. 29, pp. 1382–1392).